

SMART COMPOSITE PRODUCTION LINE PLANNING USING AI BASED DIGITAL TWIN TO OPTIMIZE THE PRODUCTION PLANNING UNDER UNCERTAINTY

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Keywords: Digital Twin, Machine learning, Production planning, Scenario based optimization,
Uncertainty

ABSTRACT

Various composite material production systems are inherently complex and labour-intensive, relying heavily on skilled human workers for critical tasks. This human dependency introduces significant uncertainty into production planning, with fluctuations in worker availability, process durations, and quality-related rework impacting system stability and efficiency. Traditional planning methods often fail to adapt to these dynamic conditions, highlighting the need for a more flexible and predictive approach. This study presents a novel framework that integrates Digital Twin (DT) and Machine Learning (ML) to optimize workforce allocation and production planning in composite manufacturing environments. A discrete-event simulation-based DT was developed to replicate system behaviour under varying operational conditions. An ML algorithm was used to forecast key performance indicators (KPIs), while a Reinforcement Learning (RL) algorithm was employed to optimize resource allocation across multiple uncertainty scenarios. The framework was applied to a real composite production line, yielding a 34% reduction in worker cost and a 16% decrease in time in system, without compromising throughput. The results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed approach in supporting resilient, data-driven decision-making for human-centric composite manufacturing systems.

1 INTRODUCTION

Global competition and increasing customer demands compel modern production, assembly, and logistics systems to become more efficient, responsive, and adaptive. These complex systems involve dynamic interactions between numerous components, making their behaviour difficult to predict using traditional analytical methods alone. To evaluate potential improvements and validate operational strategies, simulation-based approaches are often required to capture the evolving behaviour of such systems [1,2].

In parallel, the rise of Industry 4.0—driven by the integration of digital technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), and cloud computing—has transformed how industrial systems are designed and managed. One of the most prominent concepts emerging from this digital transformation is the Digital Twin (DT) [3].

A Digital Twin is a virtual representation of a physical asset, process, or system that enables real-time monitoring, predictive analysis, and informed decision-making. DTs have found widespread application in manufacturing, where they support functions such as production control, asset management, and predictive maintenance. Recent studies have explored various aspects of DT development, including their architecture, lifecycle integration, software platforms, and industrial impact [4].

This study focuses on the development and application of a Digital Twin framework within a composite manufacturing system (CMS)—a production environment known for its high complexity, process variability, and dependence on human labour. In such systems, production planning is especially

challenging due to uncertainties in worker availability, process durations, and output quality. These uncertainties can lead to shifting bottlenecks, reduced throughput, and inefficient resource utilization—limitations that are often not addressed adequately by static or one-off optimization methods.

1.1 Objective

This research investigates the integration of AI-driven Digital Twin technologies into composite production systems, with a particular focus on proactive production planning (PP) under uncertainty. The objective is to enable scenario-based optimization through RL, allowing the system to simulate and evaluate a wide range of possible future states and operational conditions. By incorporating these insights, the production plan can be dynamically adjusted to improve system-level Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

The key contributions of this study are:

Assessment of Digital Twin modeling approaches and software platforms for CMS, including evaluation of features such as real-time connectivity, 3D visualization, and implementation cost.

Proposal of a reinforcement learning-based scenario analysis framework to address planning uncertainties related to human resource variability and production quality.

Application of the proposed framework to a real-world composite production case study, demonstrating its effectiveness in generating optimized and resilient production plans.

This work contributes to the growing body of knowledge on AI-enhanced Digital Twin systems and their potential to improve decision-making in complex, uncertainty-prone manufacturing environments.

2 DIGITAL TWIN

DT technology has garnered significant interest across academia and industry for its ability to support smart manufacturing within the broader Industry 4.0 paradigm. A DT is a dynamic virtual representation of a physical asset or system, enabling real-time monitoring, simulation, and optimization through the integration of physical and digital environments.

The concept of the DT was initially proposed by Dr. Michael Grieves in 2003, comprising three key elements: the physical product, the virtual product, and the data connections between them. NASA's implementation of a DT for the International Space Station in 2012 marked a major milestone, demonstrating the potential of DTs to improve system design, monitoring, and maintenance. Their definition emphasized high-fidelity, multi-physics simulations informed by real-time data and predictive models [5].

Advances in AI, IoT, and cloud computing have accelerated DT adoption, enabling applications in real-time control, predictive analytics, and lifecycle management [3].

2.1 Digital Twin Architecture

Early DT architectures were limited to three elements—physical, virtual, and connection—but Tao et al. expanded this to a more comprehensive five-dimensional model including data and service layers [6]. These components collectively support the DT ecosystem:

- Physical Part: The real-world asset or system
- Virtual Part: The digital counterpart
- Connection: Real-time communication between the two
- Data: Collected via IoT and manufacturing systems
- Service: The computational intelligence for decision-making
- Modern manufacturing generates massive volumes of heterogeneous data from sensors, supply chains, and user interactions. Managing and integrating these datasets is foundational to effective DT implementation.

2.2 Modeling Approaches for Digital Twin

Modeling is critical for DT development as it determines the system's semantics, structure, and behavior. A variety of modeling approaches have been proposed [7-11]:

- UML and SysML: Useful for system-level design and stakeholder communication but limited in execution semantics.
- Object-Oriented Modeling: Widely used in DTs for encapsulating state and behavior but requires additional tools for simulation.
- Petri Nets and Colored Petri Nets (CPN): Effective for modeling discrete event systems and concurrency, though limited in visualization.
- Functional Mock-up Units (FMUs): Promote interoperability between simulation tools via standard interfaces.
- Ontologies: Structure heterogeneous data and improve semantic integration in DTs across lifecycles.
- Knowledge Graphs: Enhance data connectivity and inferencing capabilities by organizing relationships and attributes.
- AutomationML: Supports data exchange between manufacturing tools and preserves engineering semantics.

Despite this variety, a lack of standardized, reusable, and holistic DT development methodologies remains a key limitation. Current implementations often omit key parameters (e.g., input/output configurations) and offer little support for integration across the full system lifecycle.

2.3 Digital Twin Applications in Manufacturing

DT applications are most prevalent in manufacturing, covering multiple stages of the product lifecycle—from design to retirement. Applications include [3]:

- Design: Virtual prototyping, simulation, and optimization
- Manufacturing: Production control, resource allocation, workpiece quality prediction, and real-time monitoring
- Service: Predictive maintenance, diagnostics, and system health monitoring
- End-of-life: Dismantling, reuse, and recycling planning

In the manufacturing stage, DTs enable real-time data collection from machines and human operators, which can be used to compute and optimize Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). These KPIs serve as the basis for evaluating system performance and guiding continuous improvement initiatives.

The benefits of DT adoption include improved production efficiency, fault prediction, optimized scheduling, and enhanced decision-making.

2.4 Software Platforms for Digital Twin Implementation

Various software platforms support DT development, each with strengths tailored to different use cases. These platforms fall into four categories [11-16]:

- Discrete Event Simulation (DES) Tools: General-purpose simulation platforms (e.g., Arena, AnyLogic) using historical data and system logic modeling.
- Manufacturing Simulation Software: Tools with domain-specific capabilities, real-time data integration, and enhanced visualization (e.g., Siemens Plant Simulation, FlexSim).
- IoT Platforms: Focused on live system monitoring with cloud integration and real-time dashboards (e.g., Azure Digital Twins, AWS IoT TwinMaker).
- Other Tools: Specialized software not fitting above categories, often including AR/VR or 3D modeling (e.g., Unity, Dassault 3DEXPERIENCE).

Software capabilities are often compared across features such as:

- Real-time data integration (API/IoT) [17]
- Cloud deployment
- AI/ML support
- Customizability
- 3D visualization
- Licensing and cost

Selection of the appropriate platform depends on the system's complexity, real-time requirements, and long-term integration goals. Table 1 demonstrates the available software with their modelling approaches and their pros and cons in the context of developing DT for manufacturing systems.

Table 1 Comparison of Available software's

Software	Category	Modelling Scope	Pros	Cons
Simio MathWorks(MATLAB ,Simulink) Anylogic Flexsim Simul8	Discrete Event Simulation (DES)	Mainly behaviour modelling, and basic physical modelling	Well-suited for design and experimentation. Focus on system level and general flow. Abstract level of detail. In most cases, based on historical data. Easier to develop and implement. In most cases, cheaper than other types.	Limited support for real-time data. Limited level of detail Limited features for modelling complex systems
Ansys Twin Builder Siemens Tecnomatix Dassault DELMIA	Manufacturing Simulation	Behaviour, physical, and geometric Simulation based	Can be used to simulate running factories or design new ones. High level of detail. A wider range of features related to the manufacturing industry. Ability to simulate real-world conditions. Support real-time data and historical data.	More complex to develop. In most cases, more expensive than DES.
AWS IoT TwinMaker Azure Digital Twins Siemens Mindsphere PTC ThingWorx	IoT Platform	Data Driven	Best suited for running factories that do not require simulation. Real-time data from sensors and IoT devices. Cloud-based. Usually for monitoring and control.	More complex to develop and use. Limited simulation features
Unity	Animation	Physical, and geometric. Simulation- Based	An interactive environment. - Cross-platform support (a wide range of platforms including Augmented Reality/Virtual Reality devices).	More complex to develop. Not focused on simulation.

3. MODELING AND MANAGING UNCERTAINTY IN DIGITAL TWIN SYSTEMS

Composite material manufacturing systems are inherently uncertain, due in part to their dependence on human labor and variable curing or quality conditions [17]. DTs, while powerful, must be integrated with robust uncertainty modeling techniques to remain effective under real-world conditions.

- Uncertainty in DT systems can be broadly categorized as:

- Stochastic Uncertainty [18]: Inherent randomness in system parameters such as worker arrival times and task durations. Modelled using probabilistic distributions.
- Epistemic Uncertainty [19]: Incomplete knowledge of system behaviour or input conditions. Addressed using Bayesian inference methods.

Aleatory Uncertainty: Intrinsic variability that is irreducible [20] (e.g., raw material inconsistencies).

4. FRAMEWORK

This study presents an integrated framework that combines DT and RL to optimize production planning (PP) in a composite manufacturing system (CMS). The framework is designed to handle uncertainties—particularly in human resource availability—through scenario-based learning and optimization.

The approach consists of the following key steps:

Development of a DT using Discrete Event Simulation (DES) to simulate CMS operations.

Integration of RL to model and predict uncertain parameters, such as workforce availability and task durations.

Scenario generation using ML/RL based on historical and predicted uncertainties.

Simulation of production outcomes under different scenarios to assess their impact on key performance indicators (KPIs).

Optimization of production plans and worker allocation policies using RL, aiming to improve KPIs such as throughput, cycle time, and resource utilization.

The framework was implemented and validated on a real-world composite production line. KPIs such as production output, bottleneck reduction, and worker utilization were prioritized. All DT and RL components were developed in MathWorks and cross-validated using a Simio-based DT model to ensure robustness and accuracy.

4.1 Digital Twin Development

The DT serves as a virtual replica of the production line, enabling real-time simulation and analysis [21]. It provides insight into several KPIs, including Production throughput, Bottleneck identification, Cycle time and Worker utilization.

The DT was modeled using Discrete Event Simulation (DES) to capture dynamic system behavior and task sequences. Each production station, task duration, and resource dependency were modelled with high granularity, enabling assessment of operational performance under various conditions.

A significant innovation in this research was the dual-platform validation of the DT. While the main model was developed in MathWorks, it was independently validated using a Simio-based DT. This addresses a known challenge in DT research—lack of standard validation methods—and strengthens confidence in the simulation accuracy and results.

4.2 Scenario Analysis

Scenario analysis was used to evaluate how uncertainty in parameters related to human resource affects system-wide KPIs. The DT enabled dynamic simulation of task sequences, human-machine interaction, and queue formation between stations. The key KPIs analyzed include:

Resource utilization

Queue length minimization

Production volume maximization

The scenario analysis methodology included the following components:

Historical data integration: Real production and workforce data can be used to model variability in task durations and attendance patterns.

ML-based forecasting: An ML model can be trained on historical data to predict future workforce availability and its downstream effects on production.

Scenario generation and simulation:

A range of scenarios can be created based on predicted workforce variability. These scenarios can be simulated within the DT to assess their effects on system KPIs.

This process enabled the system to evaluate not only likely but also unseen edge-case scenarios, facilitating resilient production planning.

4.3 Optimization Using Reinforcement Learning

To optimize production planning, particularly worker allocation across stations, the framework employed a Reinforcement Learning (RL) algorithm. This model was trained in the DT environment, which allowed it to:

- Learn from simulated feedback in a risk-free setting
- Adaptively adjust policies to meet changing operational conditions
- Optimize KPIs under uncertainty
- The RL model’s objective function is targeted: Maximizing throughput, minimizing total worker cost, and Reducing time in system for each product on average.

By leveraging DT for safe experimentation and RL for adaptive decision-making, the framework supports data-driven, scenario-aware, and resilient production planning.

5. CASE STUDY

To validate the proposed framework, a real-world composite manufacturing system (CMS) was modeled. Due to confidentiality agreements, the name of the partner company is withheld. The production system consists of seven interconnected stations, each historically staffed with dedicated operators using a static, manually scheduled workforce assignment.

The developed Digital twin in MathWorks and Simio are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 respectively.

Figure 1. Developed Digital twin in MathWorks

Figure 1. a) Developed Digital twin in Simio b) Developed Dashboard in Simio for Digital Twin

A new category of flexible, multi-skilled shop-floor workers was introduced. These workers are capable of operating across multiple stations, albeit at a higher wage. The key objective was to determine an optimal workforce allocation strategy that balances throughput (T), total worker cost (C), and time in system (TIS). These KPIs were prioritized based on the factory's operational strategy: throughput (60%), worker cost (30%), and TIS (10%).

5.1 Human Resource Uncertainty and Modelling Enhancements

The subjected CMS faces operational uncertainty primarily due to two factors:

- Variability in human resource availability (e.g., sick leave, absenteeism)
- Quality-induced rework which reintroduces components back into the production flow

These uncertainties significantly impact production schedules and system stability. To address this, the Digital Twin (DT) was enhanced with features that simulate the effects of rework and human resource fluctuations. This new version extended the previously developed model by adding:

- Dynamic modeling of worker types and availability
- Simulation of 81 interdependent processes, both sequential and parallel
- Time variability per task and resource-based processing times
- Movement and behavior of workers and products
- Modeling of station capacity constraints
- Automatic dynamic allocation of workers
- Full 3D visual animation
- A live KPI dashboard and WIP (work-in-progress) metrics

These enhancements allowed for robust scenario generation and simulation across a broad range of operational conditions.

5.2 Scenario Analysis Using Machine Learning

A data-driven scenario analysis was conducted to quantify the impact of human resource uncertainty on system performance and identify optimal worker allocation strategies.

Applied Methodology:

- Historical data on worker attendance and production variability in ERP was used to train the ML model.
- An ML model was developed to predict system performance under varying worker availability and process durations.
- The Digital Twin simulated hundreds of production scenarios incorporating predicted variations.
- Scenario results informed the reinforcement learning optimization process.

This enabled a nuanced understanding of how shifts in workforce capacity influenced production bottlenecks, queue lengths, and throughput.

5.3 Reinforcement Learning-Based Optimization

The optimization process used a Reinforcement Learning (RL) framework. The framework included:

- Simulation Dataset Generation: A year's worth of possible worker availability combinations (~11,250 scenarios) was generated using the DT.
- ML-Based Performance Prediction: The ML model forecasted KPIs based on simulated outcomes.
- RL Agent Optimization: The RL agent iteratively adjusted worker allocations.

Rewards were calculated using the weighted objective function based on throughput, worker cost and time in the system for each product.

Through multiple training episodes, the agent learned to maximize throughput while minimizing costs and delays.

5.4 Key Outcomes and Impact

The integration of DT with RL enabled a robust, data-driven framework for resilient workforce planning in a high-variability environment. Compared to baseline operations:

- Worker costs were reduced by 34%
- System time was reduced by 16%
- No negative impact on throughput, despite labor constraints

These findings demonstrate the potential of combining simulation, predictive modeling, and reinforcement learning to achieve adaptive, cost-effective, and scalable production strategies in human-intensive manufacturing systems.

The case study also confirmed the feasibility of conducting advanced optimization in a risk-free virtual environment, with actionable insights ready to be applied to real operations. Future work will extend this framework to include additional constraints (e.g., maintenance schedules, product customization) and explore real-time decision-making integrations.

6. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a scenario-driven optimization framework that integrates Digital Twin (DT), Machine Learning (ML), and Reinforcement Learning (RL) to enhance production planning in a human-intensive composite manufacturing system. The proposed approach addressed key uncertainties related to human resource availability and process variability, which are common challenges in such manufacturing environments.

A DT model, developed and validated across two platforms, was used to simulate dynamic operations and generate realistic production scenarios. A ML model predicted performance metrics under varying conditions, enabling the RL agent to explore and optimize worker allocation strategies efficiently.

The framework was validated through a real-world case study, demonstrating significant reductions in total worker cost (34%) and time in system (16%), while maintaining maximum achievable throughput under existing capacity constraints. These results highlight the value of integrating data-driven decision-making tools within virtual environments for resilient and efficient production planning.

Future work will focus on extending this framework to real-time decision support and incorporating additional production constraints, further improving its applicability in dynamic and complex manufacturing settings.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This paper acknowledges the support of ACM CRC in funding this research.

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